

SIMETHIS-Flore-CBNMed - Database of Southeastern France vegetation

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Abstract

The SIMETHIS-Flore-CBNMed database (GIVD EU-FR-006) is a regional database managed by the Conservatoire Botanique National Méditerranéen dealing with occurrence data of the vascular flora of Southeastern France. It covers the following departments: Pyrénées-Orientales, Aude, Hérault, Gard, Lozère, Vaucluse, Bouches-du-Rhône, Var and Alpes-Maritimes. It includes around 19,300 phytosociological relevés of various vegetation types from the mediterranean coastal area to the alpine vegetation belt. Vegetation plots are unpublished relevés as well as digitized data from bibliographic sources (around 310 references). Almost all relevés are geolocalized. The oldest ones date from 1915 and the most recent from 2021 and the integration of new data is done continuously. The taxonomical scheme follows the French national taxonomic repository TAXREF (currently v.15). The database is part of the European Vegetation Archive under semi-restricted regime and will be updated every year. Some of the bibliographic data featured in SIMETHIS-Flore-CBNMed may also be present in SOPHY database (EU-FR-003). All the bibliographic data of SIMETHIS-Flore-CBNMed undergo a curation process regarding georeferencing, taxonomic nomenclature updates and syntaxonomic interpretation.

Abbreviations: CBNMed: Conservatoire Botanique National Méditerranéen.

Keywords

France, Mediterranean, relevé, submediterranean, vegetation database

GIVD Fact Sheet

GIVD Database ID: EU-FR-006		Last update: 2022-03-30	
SIMETHIS-Flore-CBNMed		Web address: http://simethis.eu	
Database manager(s): Guilhem De Barros (g.debarros@cbnmed.fr); Virgile Noble (v.noble@cbnmed.fr)			
Owner: Information about data owners of each relevé is available upon request. Most of the data are public but some are private.			
Scope: The database contains published and unpublished floristic occurrences and vegetation relevés from Southeastern France (Pyrénées-Orientales, Aude, Hérault, Gard, Lozère, Vaucluse, Bouches-du-Rhône, Var & Alpes-Maritimes departments). The data is collected or digitized as part of the Conservatoire Botanique National Méditerranéen (CBNMed) activities. It includes contextual and ecological information in addition to the actual relevés.			
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Availability: according to a specific agreement		Online upload: no	Online search: no
Database format(s): PostgreSQL		Export format(s): CSV file, plain text file	
Plot type(s): normal plots		Plot-size range (m²): 0.5 to 10000	
Non-overlapping plots: 19315	Estimate of existing plots: 19315	Completeness: 100%	Status: ongoing capture
Total no. of plot observations: 19315	Number of sources (biblioreferences, data collectors): 310	Valid taxa: 5128	
Countries (%): FR: 100			
Formations:			
Guilids: all vascular plants: 100%; bryophytes (terricolous or aquatic): 3%; lichens (terricolous or aquatic): 1%; algae (terricolous or aquatic): 2%			
Environmental data (%): altitude: 73; slope aspect: 52; slope inclination: 22; surface cover other than plants (open soil, litter, bare rock etc.): 4			
Performance measure(s): presence/absence only: 3%; cover: 97%			
Geographic localisation: GPS coordinates (precision 25 m or less): 64%; point coordinates less precise than GPS, up to 1 km: 31%; political units or only on a coarser scale (above 10 km): 3%			
Sampling periods: before 1920: 0.1%; 1920-1929: 0.3%; 1930-1939: 3%; 1940-1949: 2%; 1950-1959: 4%; 1960-1969: 3%; 1970-1979: 16%; 1980-1989: 3%; 1990-1999: 4%; 2000-2009: 12%; 2010-2019: 50%; unknown: 0.1%			
Information as of 2022-03-30; further details and future updates available from http://www.givd.info/ID/EU-FR-006			

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